

Health Psychology for a Sustainable Future

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Emotional regulation and executive functions in healthy adults

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Background: Emotional regulation is an individual's ability to identify, understand and accept their emotional experiences, to control impulsive behavior and to flexibly change their emotional responses.

Method: Our study aimed to determine whether there are differences between two emotion regulation processes with regard to sociodemographic variables and whether there are correlations between them and executive functions in healthy adults. The Emotional Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) and the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function - Adult Version (BRIEF-A) were administered on a community sample comprising 176 participants aged 18-70 years (mean age 26.07 years, SD 9.81; 68.8% female).

Findings: Our results showed that older participants scored higher on the CR subscale compared to younger participants. No statistically significant correlation between the ERQ subscales and education was obtained. Women attained higher CR scores than men. Five dimensions of the BRIEF-A (Shifting, Initiating, Working Memory, Planning, Organization of Materials) and total score showed statistically significant correlations with the CR. ES subscale showed a statistically significant correlation only with the Planning dimension.

Discussion: Our study found that improved emotion management skills were associated with higher executive functioning. Part of the explanation certainly lies in the fact that emotional development relies on cognitive abilities, including executive function, which is largely influenced by the maturation of the frontal lobe, which enables the voluntary, effortful control of behavior.